

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF PROPERLY SELECTED METHODS AND TECHNIQUES IN THE ACTIVITY OF THE PROPAGANDA SYSTEM

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РЕЗЮМЕ

Мақолада замонавий тарғибот системаларининг ўзига хос хусусиятлари таҳлил қилинади ва уларнинг таркиби, асосий вазифалари аниқлаб берилди. Муаллифнинг фикрига кўра, бугунги кунга келиб, улар геополитик мақсадларга хизмат қиладиган механизмга айландилар.

РЕЗЮМЕ

В статье проанализирована специфика современных систем адвокатуры, определены их структура, основные функции. По словам автора, они и по сей день превратились в механизм, служащий геополитическим целям.

SUMMARY

The article analyzes the specifics of modern advocacy systems and identifies their structure, main functions. According to the author, to this day, they have become a mechanism that serves geopolitical purposes.

Таянч сўзлар: тарғибот, замонавий тарғибот системалари, тарғибот субъекти, молиявий асослари, тарғибот вазифалари

Keywords: propaganda, modern advocacy systems, subject of propaganda, financial bases, propaganda tasks

Ключевые слова: пропаганда, современные системы защиты, предмет пропаганды, финансовые основы, пропагандистские задачи

The pace of economic development is declining in regions where the interests of geopolitical blocs collide, the social situation is deteriorating, and people's living conditions are worsening. Over the past eight years, such a situation has been observed in Tunisia, Libya, Egypt, Jordan, Syria, Iraq, Lebanon, Yemen, Afghanistan, Ukraine, Moldova, and other countries. Ensuring the real independence of countries and protecting it from falling under the influence of geopolitical powers has become a strategic task for all states.

The disruption of the balance between geopolitical forces is always caused by a social event that has a global impact. In our time, such a process is represented

by the global financial and economic crisis that began in the United States in 2008 and subsequently affected countries around the world.

In general, social crises have occurred many times throughout human history. According to Professor F. Kening of Oxford University, the first social crisis occurred in the year 88 BC in the Roman Empire." "As we entered the new century, the nature of all types of propaganda changed fundamentally. Its social significance increased, its goals took on a new content, its application scope expanded, and it became a powerful tool used on a global scale by various social groups and political forces to achieve their objectives. This did not happen spontaneously, of course. Changes in the propaganda system occurred under the influence of several social processes, trends, and factors. Among these, the geopolitical competition that sharply escalated by the early 21st century became a decisive factor. Therefore, to identify the changes in the propaganda system, it is necessary to analyze it in the context of geopolitical competition at the beginning of the 21st century. For this purpose, it is essential to study the reasons that led to the intensification of competition among geopolitical powers and its consequences.

When referring to geopolitical powers, we mean centers of power that attempt to influence global processes, steer them towards their interests, and enhance their positions in various regions. Such powers have existed throughout all periods of human social development. From this perspective, the history of humanity can be viewed as a continuous process of the successive replacement of geopolitical periods dominated by various geopolitical forces. For instance, in the ancient world, Rome and Carthage emerged as geopolitical powers, while in the Middle Ages, powerful empires that arose in the East and West took their place. In the modern era, Spain, Portugal, and the Netherlands, and later England, France, and Sweden, became part of such powers. By the 20th century, the unification of geopolitical powers into blocks became common. For example, at the beginning of the century, Germany, Austria-Hungary, and Italy united into the Triple Alliance, forming a powerful geopolitical block, while the Entente, consisting of France, England, and Russia, emerged as a rival geopolitical block. On the eve of World War II, Germany and its allies formed one geopolitical block, while the USSR, the USA, England, and their allies formed a second geopolitical block. After World War II, a period known as the "bipolar world" lasted for nearly half a century. This period was marked by the geopolitical rivalry between the USSR and the USA.

In all periods, geopolitical powers have aimed to "divide the world," clearly delineate the regions under their influence, and promote their own development models and value systems in various regions. The spheres of influence of geopolitical powers and the fundamental rules of their interactions have been recorded in various documents. For instance, the relations between geopolitical powers and the rules of their interactions were noted at the Congress of Vienna in 1814-1815, the Treaty of Versailles in 1919, and the Potsdam Agreement in 1945. However, each time these documents were violated by the will of one of the parties, ultimately leading to the disruption of the geopolitical balance in the world.

In the second half of the 20th century, the geopolitical situation in the world changed again. The establishment of the European Union, the collapse of the USSR, changes in the character of social development in China, and a number of similar events led to the emergence of a new configuration of geopolitical powers. Today, the activities of three main geopolitical blocks are becoming increasingly prominent:

- a) The USA and Great Britain;
- b) The European Union;
- c) The Russia-China alliance.

Additionally, it should be noted that in recent years, leading countries in Latin America and states referred to as "Asian Tigers" are also emerging as independent geopolitical powers.

The main objectives of these geopolitical powers continue to be: a) to change global processes in accordance with their interests and to create favorable situations; b) to keep the socio-economic development of other geopolitical powers under control.¹ "Experts mention nearly ten crises that emerged in the 20th century. For example, the socio-economic crisis that occurred in developed countries of Europe from 1900 to 1903 led to a sharp decline in production levels. The crisis known as the 'Great Depression' began in the United States in 1929, lasted for a decade, and gradually had a negative impact on the industries of Canada, Great Britain, Germany, and France. In Russia, the crisis that arose in 1923 due to the imbalance between the prices of industrial and agricultural products ended with severe consequences. Additionally, the oil crisis of 1973, the Asian stock market crisis of 1997-1998, and similar events had a serious impact on the pace of social development. However, among them, the global financial and economic crisis that began in 2008 and whose effects are still not fully eliminated in some countries and

sectors has been particularly significant in terms of its scale, social, economic, and political consequences.

'Today,' said I. Karimov during the initial phase of the financial and economic crisis, 'the world economy is experiencing the most difficult period in its development over the last decade. The world has faced a financial and economic crisis that has affected almost all countries for the first time.'¹

Experts indicate various reasons for this crisis. Naturally, the financial and economic crisis arose under the influence of a number of social, economic, political, and spiritual-cultural factors. Among these, it is particularly important to highlight the deepening consumer mentality among U.S. citizens.

The emergence of this consumer mentality is related to the social processes that occurred in European countries in the second half of the 19th century. During this period, the rising dissatisfaction among the population and the decline in the standard of living of citizens not only led to a change in the ruling circles but also caused a transformation in the social hierarchy. The U.S. government, along with large companies and corporate owners, drew relevant conclusions from these processes. They began to pay special attention to meeting the daily needs of citizens and providing them with essential consumer goods. The emergence of such an industry served, on one hand, to ensure stability in the country, and on the other hand, it also increased the revenues of companies. As a result, by the beginning of the 20th century, products that had previously only been available to a select few became everyday consumer goods.

Additionally, in Western Europe and the U.S., doctrines that justified and glorified people's hedonistic aspirations and consumer mentality also developed. The transformation of goal-oriented activities into a life strategy, evaluating intelligence as a value that implements tactics for achieving success, the pursuit of methods that allow for the resolution of problematic situations and adaptation to social conditions rather than identifying the foundations of existence, understanding reality as a relative concept subject to specific interests, using a rational ethics that serves to improve one's social status, and recognizing individual needs and interests as primary values.

Doctrines such as instrumentalism, operationalism, pragmatism, and positivism (later neopositivism and post-positivism) have provided a foundation for justifying humanity's consumerist relationship with the world, creating a basis for the deep roots of consumer mentality. Consumerism has become the main criterion defining the lifestyle in the Western world.

The formation of the consumer goods industry and the widespread promotion of consumer psychology have accustomed Western individuals to adopt a consumerist attitude towards everything. Even the mismatch between product prices and personal material and financial capabilities could not deter them from consumerism—this situation gave rise to a myriad of credit systems to assist them. Housing, automobiles, luxury goods, appliances, and technical devices became items that were purchased on credit.

Citizens began to evaluate and satisfy their housing needs from the perspective of consumer quality. In situations where individuals had limited financial means, the demand to meet these needs through mortgage loans increasingly grew. In response, the U.S. Federal Reserve System offered over 500 new forms of credit to consumers from 2000 to 2008, lowered the credit score requirements from 800 to 500, and even allowed 14-year-old boys and girls to obtain loans. Such support for housing demand created a continuous rise in prices in the housing market. For example, in Boston, the cost of housing per square meter was \$3,000 in 2002, but by 2005 it had surged to \$10,000. At the same time, construction companies were also adequately funded by bank loans. Ultimately, by 2008, a situation emerged in the housing market where supply exceeded demand. Following the 'domino' principle, this led to defaults on funds in banks, a decline in liquidity levels, bank bankruptcies, the onset of a nationwide financial crisis, and the transition of the crisis from the financial sector to the economy as a whole. Within six months, the U.S. financial and economic crisis spread to other countries and took on a global character.¹

The crisis led to dire consequences. All major banks, along with investment banks, halted any lending. This did not save many large banks from disaster: one by one, these financial institutions began to declare themselves bankrupt. Soon, the crisis transitioned from the financial sector to the economy. The sharp decline in the amount of credit allocated for production and consumer goods negatively impacted many giants. For instance, the cessation of loans for purchasing vehicles led to a significant reduction in production volumes at auto giants like Opel and Ford. The financial crisis also affected the traditional energy sources market: the price of oil on the global market fell from \$147 per barrel to \$40.

Most notably, the financial-economic crisis created a foundation for the decline of global economic indicators. For example, global trade contracted by 10% in 2008-2009. A decrease in gross national income was observed in all developed countries. Admittedly, the situation seemed to improve somewhat in

2011; however, the economic recession that began in the fall of that year led to a prolonged negative dynamic.

The crisis resulted in a decline in economic indicators in both developed and developing countries, followed by a rise in social problems. Even in developed countries such as the U.S., Germany, England, Italy, France, Japan, and Canada, the real incomes of citizens began to decrease as a result of the crisis. Many social programs were temporarily halted, citizens' dissatisfaction with the existing situation grew, and the unemployment rate increased. In developing countries in Europe, Asia, Africa, and Latin America, the situation became unprecedentedly severe.

In such a situation, among developed countries, there was a growing sentiment to leverage the existing economic, financial, and especially energy resources for their own interests to escape the consequences of the crisis, and to attempt to alter the global situation in line with their own interests. This fundamentally changed the balance of power in the geopolitical arena and the competition between geopolitical blocs. Today, this competition encompasses all areas of social life. Interestingly, geopolitical powers are not only limited to realizing their interests but are also striving to justify them with modern propaganda factors and means.

In conclusion, the financial-economic crisis that emerged in 2008 significantly intensified the mutual competition between various geopolitical blocs. Geopolitical powers, whose fundamental goals consist of gaining global leadership and altering global processes in a way that aligns with their interests, have begun to view propaganda as a tool for achieving geopolitical objectives in the new century. For instance, in economic competition, propaganda has become a means of justifying the positions of geopolitical powers on the global economic stage; in political competition, it serves as a factor that integrates their state symbols, forms, and political regimes; in social competition, it acts as a channel for promoting desirable lifestyles; and in ideological competition, it transforms into a powerful means of disseminating the ideas, doctrines, traditions, and values they are interested in.

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